

Spectrophotometric Determination of 2,2-Dichlorovinyl dimethyl Phosphate (DDVP) and its Application in Water, Soil and Vegetables

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A method has been developed for the spectrophotometric determination of 2,2-dichlorovinyl dimethyl phosphate (DDVP), an insecticide, based on its alkaline hydrolysis to produce dichloroacetaldehyde, yielding a fluorescent yellow coloured dye with J acid when heated in concentrated sulphuric acid medium. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of DDVP in water, soil and vegetables.

2,2-DICHLOROVINYLDIMETHYL phosphate (DDVP), also known as dichlorovos, is a well-known organophosphorus insecticide¹, and it is highly toxic². Methods used for the determination of DDVP generally involve the use of infrared spectroscopy, gas chromatography, thin layer chromatography, polarography etc.³. Most of the photometric methods of determination of DDVP are based on the alkaline hydrolysis of DDVP to produce dichloroacetaldehyde and its subsequent reaction with resorcinol⁴ or 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine⁵. These methods have poor sensitivity and higher blank problem^{4,5}. Similarly, the cholinesterase method⁶ is non-selective as all organophosphorus group containing pesticides interfere.

This communication reports a sensitive method for the determination of DDVP based on the alkaline hydrolysis of DDVP to form dichloroacetaldehyde as described by Hughes⁶. Dichloroacetaldehyde reacts with J acid in concentrated H₂SO₄ medium, which is very sensitive for the determination of formaldehyde⁷. Chromotropic acid, another reagent for the determination of formaldehyde, also gives test with dichloroacetaldehyde, but it is not as sensitive as J acid. This reaction of J acid with dichloroacetaldehyde gives fluorescent yellow coloured dye having λ_{\max} at 470 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 10–100 μg of DDVP in 10 ml of final volume (1–10 ppm). The method has been successfully applied for the determination of DDVP in water, soil and vegetables. Other organophosphorus pesticides, such as malathion, monocrotophos and other pesticides do not interfere with the proposed method.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss specol with 1 cm matched glass cells was used.

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of DDVP (HCG, India) was prepared in ethanol and working stan-

dard solution (20 μg ml⁻¹) was prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.2% J acid (6-amino-1-naphthol-3-sulphonic acid) (Wilson) solution was prepared in concentrated H₂SO₄. A 1 M NaOH solution was made in deionized water.

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and deionised water was used.

Procedure: An aliquot of standard solution containing 10–100 μg of DDVP was evaporated to 0.5 ml in a water-bath and then kept in ice-water. To it 1M NaOH (0.5 ml) was added and left for 15 min for complete hydrolysis. Then a 0.2% J acid solution (2 ml) was added dropwise and placed in boiling water-bath for ~ 20 min. The solution was cooled and made upto 10 ml with concentrated H₂SO₄. The absorbance of dye was measured at 470 nm against a reagent blank (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of the dye : (A) concentration of DDVP = 76 $\mu\text{g}/10$ ml and (B) reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables: For optimum results, 15 min for hydrolysis and 20 min for heating were required. Increase in heating time showed no

adverse effects. Hydrolysis of dichloroacetaldehyde was quantitative at 0°. The reaction of dichloroacetaldehyde with J acid was found to be maximum at 100° and above and hence, it was carried out in boiling water. For complete hydrolysis and full colour development 0.5 ml of 1M NaOH and 2 ml of 0.2% J acid were adequate.

Spectral characteristics: Beer's law is obeyed in the range 10–100 µg of DDVP in 10 ml of final volume (1–10 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $6.63 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0033 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.013 and $\pm 4.33\%$ respectively for a 40 µg/10 ml solution of DDVP analysed over a period of eight days.

Effect of contaminants: Effects of various interfering co-pollutants and pesticides were studied by adding known amount of these to a 10 ml solution containing 40 µg of DDVP. Several metal ions and pesticides did not interfere with this method. The tolerance limits (in ppm) of various foreign species associated with 4 ppm of DDVP are as follows: Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} (60); Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Cd^{II} (30); K and chloride (25); Sb^{III} and parathion (50); fluoride (125); kelthane (90); cyanide and acrylonitrile (250); malathion and BHC (500).

Application: To check the validity of the method, synthetic samples were prepared by adding known amounts of DDVP in water, and vegetable soil samples. The samples were fortified with DDVP and kept for 12 h. DDVP was then extracted with solvent (2×25 ml) diethyl ether (in case of soil and water) or carbon tetrachloride (in case of vegetables). The solvent was then evaporated off and DDVP was determined by the proposed method (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF DDVP IN WATER, SOIL AND VEGETABLES

Sample**	DDVP found originally* µg	DDVP added* µg	DDVP found* µg	Recovery %
Water ^a	6.00	20	19.60	98.00
	4.00	40	39.00	97.50
	1.50	80	78.00	97.50
Soil ^b	2.00	20	19.40	97.50
	5.50	40	39.50	98.75
	8.00	80	79.00	98.75
Cauliflower ^b	7.00	20	19.50	97.50
	6.50	40	38.70	96.75
	3.00	80	78.60	98.25
Tomato ^b	9.00	20	19.40	97.00
	3.50	40	39.50	98.75
	5.00	80	79.50	99.37

*Mean of three replicate analyses. **Amount of sample
^a250 ml; ^b50 g.

The proposed method was also applied for the determination of DDVP in water, soil and vegetable samples already contaminated with DDVP. These samples were extracted with appropriate solvents, which was then evaporated off and DDVP was determined by the present method (Table 1).

The results (Table 2) show that the present method is more sensitive and suitable for determination of DDVP in environmental samples when compared with the other known methods.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF SENSITIVITY FOR DDVP WITH OTHER REAGENTS

Reagent	λ_{max} nm	Beer's law range ppm	Interferences/ remarks
Resorcinol ^a	490	1–20	Dye unstable high reagent blank
2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazine ^b	580	3.4–27.5	Lower sensitivity
Cholinesterase ^c	412	20	Interference of other organo- phosphorus pesti- cides
J acid ^d	470	1–10	Free from inter- ference of other organophosphorus pesticide

^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 5, ^cRef. 6, ^dPresent method.

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References

- G. Zweig, "Analytical Methods for Pesticides, Plant Growth Regulators", Academic, New York, 1964, Vol. 2, p. 561.
- G. S. GRUZDYEV, "The Chemical Protection of Plants", Moscow, 1983, p. 181; F. A. GUNTHER and L. R. JEPSON, "Modern Insecticides and World Food Production", 1960, p. 257.
- Ref. 1, p. 567; N. S. PODKOVRINA, R. V. VIGLOK and L. I. BUKIROVA, *Usp. Gazov. Khromatogr.*, 1978, 5, 209 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1980, H22); S. M. TEWARI and S. P. HARPALANI, *Fresenius Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1977, 48, 285; J. DAVDEK, J. SCIFERT and DELEZALOVA, *Mitteilungen der Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1976, 31, 267 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1977, F49).
- J. R. RANGASWAMY and M. MUTHU, *Microchim. Acta*, 1984, 3, 433.
- J. T. HUGHES, *Analyst*, 1963, 88, 318.
- V. DREVENKAR, Z. VASILIC and Z. STEFANCE, *Microchim. Acta*, 1981, 2, 45.
- S. EUGENE, R. H. THOMAS and M. SYLVESTAR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 1460.